

Jolo Municipal Government: Issues, Concerns and Prospects of Management on Market and Sidewalk Vendors

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Publication Date: June 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16563405

Abstract

This study sought to determine the extent of market management and market vendors' perceptions toward the public market programs, vis-à-vis administration and supervision, safety and security, hygiene and sanitation, prohibit acts by the market vendors, and obligatory duties and responsibilities of the market vendors. It answered the research questions based on the following hypothesis: There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to gender, age and monthly income. It employed the descriptive-quantitative research design with 20 market management and 100 market vendors in Jolo, Sulu. The mean, percentage score and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of market management and vendors' perceptions on the market management programs. The t-Test for independent samples and One-Way ANOVA were used to determine the significant differences in the perceptions of market management and vendors in the following domains such as supervision, safety and security, hygiene and sanitation, prohibit acts by the market vendors, and obligatory duties and responsibilities of the market vendors. This study revealed the following findings: I. On respondents'

demographic profiles; 1.1. In terms of gender, out of 20 market management staff. 19 are male with only one female, while out of 100 market vendors, 62 are male and 38 are female. 1.2. In terms of age, out of 20 market management staff 65% on the age range of 41 years old and above which is followed by 31-40 years old and 20-30 years old which constitute 20% and 15% respectively. Likewise, 48% out of 100 vendors are within the age range of 41 years old and above while 36% at 31-40 years old and 16% at 20-30 years old brackets. 1.3. In terms of monthly income, 67% are within the income range of 3,000-6,000 while some of them are within the 1,000-3,000 and 6,000-9,000 brackets with 18% and 15% respectively. None among the vendors earns 9,000 and above. 1.4. In terms of occupation, police and garbage collectors constitute 25% each of the total market management staff. However, among the vendors group, both vegetable/fruit and fish vendors constitute 28% each out of the 100 respondents. 2. On the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government on market and sidewalk vendors as perceived by the management and vendors: 2.1 By Management's perceptions; 2.1.1 On administration and supervision; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.2 On safety and security; this category is generally rated as Agree,

2.1.3 On Hygiene and Sanitation; this category is generally rated as Strongly Agree, 2. 1.4 On Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.5 On Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors; this category is generally rated as Agree; 2.2 By Market Vendors' perceptions 2.1.1 On administration and supervision; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.2 On safety and security; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.3 On Hygiene and Sanitation; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.4 On Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors; this category is generally rated as Agree, 2.1.5 On Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors; this category is generally rated as Agree; 3. On the differences on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors; 3.1 By Gender: There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to gender; 3.2 By Age: There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to age; 3.3 By Income: There is significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to income. And that, no other group of market vendors are supposed to have better level of perceptions than

the 6,000-9,000 monthly earners with regards to judging the proper implementation of safety and security as well as the hygiene and sanitation at the market areas of the Municipality of Jolo.

Based of the findings of this, the following conclusions are made: 1. Most of the market management staff and market vendors are male, with age range of 41 years old and above and at monthly income range of 3,000-6,000; 2. Generally, both market management staff and markets vendors agree to the programs and policies of market management of the Municipality of Jolo, Sulu; 3. Among the respondents' demographic profiles, monthly income is observed to have great influence on the ways how market management staff and market vendors perceive the extent of the programs and policies of market management of the Municipality of Jolo, Sulu; 4. Mostly the issues on security and safety, proper implementation of market laws or ordinances and prompt payment of the market fees and renewal of the licenses, proper collection of garbage and watering of the place where the fish is usually sold, are recommended by both Management and Marker and Sidewalk vendors in order to improve the Jolo Public Market; and S. This study seemed to support the theory of Hal Draper, specifically on non-state Junction which states, among others, that the government shall render social services among its constituents in the spheres of economic, social, cultural and political life.

Keywords: *Employees engagement, employees' performance, affective engagement, intellectual engagement*

INTRODUCTION

The Republic Act 7160, otherwise known as, "The Local Government Code of 1991" provides, among others, in Section 17 (Basic Services and Facilities) which emphasized that the "Local government units shall endeavor to be self-reliant and shall continue exercising the powers and discharging the duties

and functions currently vested upon them. They shall also discharge the functions and responsibilities of national agencies and offices devolved to them pursuant to this Code".

In addition, the local government units shall likewise exercise such other powers and discharge such other functions and responsibilities as are necessary, appropriate, or incidental to efficient and effective provision of the basic services and facilities.

Such basic services and facilities include the following: a) Services and facilities related to general hygiene and sanitation, beautification, and solid waste collection; b) Maintenance of Barangay roads and bridges; c) Water supply systems; d) Infrastructure facilities such as multi- purpose hall; e) Multipurpose pavement, plaza, sports center and other similar facilities; and f) The provision of Satellite or public market, where viable.

To compliment the above provisions of basic service and facilities, Senate Bill No. 1319 "An Act Instituting the National Market Code of the Philippines" was proposed by Former Senator Manny Villa. He reiterated that: Local Government Code authorizes both the Sangguniang Bayan and Sangguniang Panglungsod to regulate the preparation and sale of meat, poultry, fish, vegetables, fruits, fresh dairy products, and other foodstuffs for public consumption (Secs. 447, 5, iv and 458, 5, iv, RA 7160).

Sen. Manny Villar stressed further, that public markets are responsive and effective instruments of public service. They are also dynamic and viable enterprises which strengthen the financial capabilities of cities, municipalities, and even barangays. Thus, it has significant contribution to both national and local development.

It is in the above context, why the researcher endeavored to conduct this study, to determine the programs of Jolo Municipal Government towards the Market and its vendors that serve the rising demands of the Jolo constituents on the provisions of basic services and facilities.

METHOD

Research Design

In as much as there is a hypothesis to be validated upon the very completion of the study, the research design used therefore is a descriptive-exploratory in nature.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the Jolo, Sulu. Specifically, the locale is at Barangay Walled City where the Jolo Public Market is located. And Jolo Municipal Government, located also in the same barangay, where the Management, referred to in this study, as the Municipal officials and employees who have direct involvement in the management of the Jolo Public Market.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the market and sidewalk vendors, and the municipal employees who are involved in the management of the Jolo Public Market.

Sampling Design

This study used purposive sampling for the market and sidewalk vendors and census de jure for the Jolo municipal employees. The table below shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents according to Type of Occupation

Type of Occupation	Respondents
Management	
Mayor	1
Vice Mayor	1
Municipal Councilor	3
Municipal Treasurer	1
Market Administrator/Supervisor	1
Sanitary Inspector	1
Police/Security	5
Garbage Collector	5
Market Fees Collector	2
Subtotal	20
Vendors	
Stall Owner	16
Fish Vendor	28
Meat Vendor	6
Vegetable/Fruit Vendor	28
Dried/Salted Good Vendor	10
Others	12
Subtotal	100
Total	120

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured the permission from the Office of the Dean of the Graduate Studies, thereafter upon approval, asked the permission from the Office of the Jolo Municipal Mayor, office of the Barangay Walled City to conduct the study. The approved permit was attached in the Check-List Questionnaire, so that the concern respondents will be cognizant that this study has full knowledge and permission of the Mayor and Barangay Captain.

Research Instrument

This study used check-list questionnaire prepared by the researcher. The questionnaire is divided into three parts. The first part inquired the Demographic Profile of the respondent.

The second part is the Likert's scale type of questionnaire, where it inquired the responses of the respondents on the issues and concerns on the Jolo public market. The third part constitute the responses of the respondents on the prospects of the Jolo public market.

Validity and Reliability

Since the research instrument (check-list questionnaire) was made by the researcher himself, it sought the validation by the experts from among the professors of Sulu State College to determine the validity and reliability of the instrument, including the correctness of the grammar and its appropriateness to study.

Statistical Treatment

The research questions in this study are divided into three. Hence, the research instrument (check-list questionnaire) is also divided into three blocks. Block I is about the demographic profile of the respondent which was treated by frequency and percentage. Block II is about the overall management of the Jolo public market, where the questions are subdivided into four areas; mean and standard deviation were utilized to treat the respective data. On the question of the significance difference of the perceptions by the management, market and sidewalk vendors this study used t-test and ANOVA.

While on the prospects of development of the Solo public market, the responses of the respondents are ranked accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data gathered for this study. It also deals specifically with the socio demographic profile of market management and market sidewalk vendors at Jolo, Sulu in terms of gender, age and monthly income; the extent of market management and market sidewalk vendors' perceptions toward the public market programs, albeit administration and supervision, safety and security, hygiene and sanitation, prohibit acts by the market vendors, and obligatory duties and responsibilities of the market vendors.

Based on the appropriate scoring and statistical treatments of data acquired for this study, the following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results which correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the profile of the market management and market sidewalk vendors in terms of gender, age, monthly income and type of occupation?

1.1 By Gender

Table 2.1 shows the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 20 market management staff, 19 are male with only one female. On the other hand, out of 100 market vendors, 62 are male and 38 are female. This means that male overwhelmingly outnumbered their female counterparts in both market management and market vendors groups.

Table 2. 1 Demographic profiles of respondents in terms of gender.

Gender	Management		Vendors	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Male	19	95.00	62	62.00
Female	1	5.00	38	38.00
Total	20	100.00	100	100.00

1.2 By Age

Table 2.2 presents the demographic profiles of **respondents** in terms of age. Out of 20 market management staff, 65% on the age range of 41 years old and above which is followed by 31–40-year-old and 20-30 years old which constitute 20% and 15% respectively. Likewise, 48% out of 100 vendors are within the age range of 41 years old and above while 36% at 31-40 years old and 16% at 20–30-year-old brackets. This means that both the market management staff and vendors are within the oldest age bracket.

Table 2.2 Demographic profiles of respondents in terms of age.

Age	Management		Vendors	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
20-30 y.o	3	15.00	16	16.00
31-40 y.o	4	20.00	36	36.00
41 y.o & above	13	65.00	48	48.00
	20	100.00	100	100.00

1.3 By Income

Table 2.3 illustrates the demographic profiles of respondents in terms of monthly income. It can be noticed from the table that out of 100 vendors, 67% are within the income range of 3,000-6,000. Some of them are within the 1,000-3,000 and 6,000-9,000 brackets with 18% and 15% respectively. None among the vendors earns 9,000 and above. This means that most of the market vendors at the Municipality of Jolo are meager earners whose monthly income seems not commensurate their basic needs, to name a few, such as food, clothing, housing, medication and education of their children.

Table 2.3 Demographic profiles of respondents in terms of monthly income.

Monthly Income	Number of Vendors	Percent
1,000 – 3,000	18	18.00
3, 000 – 6,000	67	67.00
6,000 – 9,000	15	15.00
9,000 & above	0	0.00
Total	100	100.00

1.4 By type of Occupation

Table 2.4 shows the demographic profiles of respondents in terms of type of occupation. Based on the data in this table, police and garbage collectors constitute 25% each of the total market management staff. However, among the vendors group, both vegetable/fruit and fish vendors constitute 28% each out of the 100 respondents. This means that the market management has considerable numbers of security personnel and garbage collectors. Most vendors in the Public Market of the Municipality of Jolo indulge in vegetable/fruit and fish vending.

Table 2.4 Demographic profiles of respondents in terms of type of occupation

Type of Occupation	Respondents	Percent
Management		
Mayor	1	5.00
Vice Mayor	1	5.00
Municipal Councilor	3	15.00
Municipal Treasurer	1	5.00
Market Administrator/Supervisor	1	5.00
Sanitary Inspector	1	5.00
Police/Security	5	25.00
Garbage Collector	5	25.00
Market Fees Collector	2	10.00
Subtotal	20	100.00
Vendors		
Stall Owner	16	16.00
Fish Vendor	28	28.00
Meat Vendor	6	6.00
Vegetable/Fruit Vendor	28	28.00
Dried/Salted Good Vendor	10	10.00
Others	12	12.00
Subtotal	100	100.00
Total	120	100.00

2. What is the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government on market and sidewalk vendors as perceived by the management and vendors in each of the following areas: 2.1) administration and supervision, 2.2) safety and security, 2.3) hygiene and sanitation, 2.4) prohibit acts by the market vendors, and 2.5) obligatory duties and responsibilities of the market vendors.

2.1 By Management

2.1.1 On administration and supervision

Table 2.1.1 illustrates the extent of market administration and supervision as perceived by management. With overall mean score of 4.4050 and standard deviation of 36487, this category is generally rated as Agree. This means that public market management of Jolo, Sulu are akin to the policies that "The Mayor shall exercise powers of administration and supervision and control overall markets in the municipality." Similarly, the management staff believes that the market administrator shall coordinate with other offices in maintaining proper hygiene and sanitation and enforces strictly all provisions of municipal ordinances related to market administration.

Table 2.1.1 Extent of market administration and supervision as perceived by management

No	Administration and Supervision	Mean	SD	Description
1	The Mayor shall exercise powers of administration and supervision and control overall markets in the municipality.	2.550	.51042	Strongly Agree

2	The treasurer accepts and records all application for markets stall.	4.450 0	.60481	Agree
3	The treasurer shall be responsible for awards of stall, collect and receive all kinds of rentals, including license and taxes.	4.200 0	.69585	Agree
4	The market administrator shall have the direct and immediate supervision over the market, slaughter	4.100 0	.55251	Agree
5	The market administrator shall exercise immediate overall market collectors and other personnel in the market.	4.250 0	.63867	Agree
6	The market administrator shall coordinate with other offices in maintaining proper hygiene and sanitation and enforces strictly all provisions of municipal ordinances related to market administration.	4.600 0	.59824	Strongly Agree
7	The market administrator shall require all market collectors to turn over their respective collection every day, act as property custodian all property of the market.	4.350 0	.58714	Agree
8	The market administrator shall prohibit the building and construction in the market or premises hereof any form of extension of stalls, shade or tables beyond the lease area.	4.750 0	.44426	Strongly Agree
9	The market administrator shall inspect and supervises market and slaughter house to ensure that all livestock are properly cared for, butchered and sold in conformity with regulation of the National Meat Inspection Commission.	4.500 00	.51229	Strongly Agree
10	The market administrator shall inspect dressed meat (chicken) and determine its fitness for human consumption.	4.300 0	1.08094	Agree
Average Mean		4.405 0	.36487	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49= Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49-Uncecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49-Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.1.2 On safety and security

Table 2.1.2 presents the extent of safety and security as perceived by management. It can be noted from this table that the overall mean score of 4.3600 with standard deviation of .44768 is generally rated as Agree. This means that the market management adheres strongly to the notions that there shall be security personnel assigned in the market to ensure safe and secured market environment. Moreover, the belief of the market management is that the security personnel shall report violation of laws, ordinances to proper law enforcing agencies.

Table 2. 1.2 Extent of safety and security as perceived by management

No	Safety and Security	Mean	SD	Description
1	There shall be security personnel assigned in the market to ensure safe and secured market environment.	4.5500	.51042	Strongly Agree
2	The security personnel shall patrol and perform sentinel activity within the market and slaughter house premises.	4.4500	.51042	Agree
3	The security personnel shall report violation of laws, ordinances to proper law enforcing agencies.	4.5000	.60698	Strong Agree
4	The security personnel shall make inventory of losses of property if there is any.	3.9500	1.09904	Agree
5	The security personnel shall sound alarms in case of emergencies and operates fire extinguisher or inform the Bureau of Fire Protection	4.3500	.74516	Agree
Average Mean		4.3600	.44768	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50- 5.00=Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49-Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49-Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49= Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.1.3 On Hygiene and Sanitation

Table 2, 1.3 expresses the extent of hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by management. With overall mean score of 4.5200 and standard deviation of .26278 is rated as Strongly Agree. This means that the market management is strongly convinced that all merchandise, goods and textiles offered for sale in the market shall be so arranged so that no portion of the alleys shall be obstructed, and that the floor stands, and all other places of things used for exposing the same can be easily and perfectly clean. Similarly, the market management strongly expressed concern that all merchandise, goods, articles or foodstuffs offered for sale shall be protected from all kinds of insects and vermin and placed in such manner as authorized by the municipal officials.

More specifically, the market management, among other things, expects that all fixed stall vendors shall install garbage receptacles in their respective stalls. Garbage and waste shall be regularly hauled to the dumpsite. Sufficient potable water shall be provided by the Municipal for use in cleaning fresh foodstuffs in the market.

Table 2. 1.3 Extent of Hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by management

No	Hygiene and Sanitation	Mean	SD	Description
1	All merchandise, goods and textiles offered for sale in the market shall be so arranged so that no portion of the alleys shall be obstructed, and the that the floor stands, and all other places of things used for exposing the same can be easily and perfectly clean.	4.7500	.444 26	Strongly Agree
2	All merchandise, goods, articles or foodstuffs offered for sale shall be protected from all kinds of insects and vermin and placed in such manner as authorized by the municipal officials.	4.5500	.510 42	Strongly Agree
3	The market cleaners will be closely supervised by the Municipal Health Officer or his representative.	4.3000	.801 31	Agree
4	Market cleaning schedule will be at night time, early dawn or noon time to prevent inconvenience to the vendors and the market going public.	4.4000	.598 24	Agree
5	All fixed stall vendors shall install garbage receptacles in their respective stalls.	4.6000	5026 2	Strongly Agree
6	Garbage and waste shall be regularly hauled to the dumpsite.	4.6500	.587 14	Strongly Agree
7	Sufficient potable water shall be provided by the Municipal for use in cleaning fresh foodstuffs in the market.	4.5500	5104 2	Strongly Agree
8	Livestock ante-mortem and post-mortem inspections of dressed meat shall be conducted before the animals are butchered and before the dressed meat a9+re taken out of the abattoir.	4.4500	.510 42	Agree
9	The meat inspector shall submit regularly reports to the local authorities on the conditions in the slaughter house.	4.3500	.489 36	Agree
10	The Municipal Health Officer is tasked with the keeping the market in a clean, healthful and sanitary condition	4.6000	.598 24	Strongly Agree
Average Mean		4.5200	.262 78	Strongly Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50 - 5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49= Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49= Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.1.4 On Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors

Table 2.1.4 shows the extent of prohibit acts by the market vendors as perceived by management. It is noticeable on this table that the overall mean score of 4.2700 with standard deviation of .26378 is generally rated as Agree. This result explains that the market management is amenable to the observations that there are rampant of selling of goods not designated in assigned areas; unauthorized making of extensions of stalls beyond leased areas and/or utilizing pathways for displays of goods which included short weighing and false measuring including tampering of standard weights and measures.

That is, the market management believes on the outright banning of littering, vandalizing and improper use of comfort rooms (if there is any) and non-observance and cooperation on cleanliness and orderliness, and displaying and selling of illegal products/items

Table 2. 1.4 Extent of prohibit acts by the market vendors as perceived by management

No	Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors	Mean	SD	Description
1	Selling of goods not designated in assigned areas.	4.6500	.48936	Strongly Agree
2	Unauthorized making of extensions of stalls beyond leased areas and/or utilizing pathways for displays of goods.	4.7500	.44426	Strongly Agree
3	Short weighing and false measuring including tampering of standard weights and measures.	4.5500	.51042	Strongly Agree
4	Bringing in motorcycles, bicycles, push carts and the like inside the market compound.	3.9500	.94451	Agree
5	Utilizing any of the stalls or market spaces as residence or living quarters.	3.8000	.83351	Agree
6	Littering, vandalizing and improper use of comfort rooms (if there is any) and non-observance and cooperation on cleanliness and orderliness.	4.5000	.60698	Strongly Agree
7	Selling or transferring the privilege to lease the stalls or spaces or permitting another person to conduct business therein.	3.8500	.87509	Agree
8	Bringing in of children below 10 years old by market vendors inside the market premises.	4.6500	.97872	Agree
9	Operation of any forms of gambling or betting a videoke machine and the like.	4.7500	.58714	Agree
10	Display and selling of illegal products/items.	4.5500	.94032	Strongly Agree
Average Mean		3.9500	.26378	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49= Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49-Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.1.5 On Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors

Table 2.1.5 shows the extent of hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by management. With mean score of 4.2100 and standard deviation of .38648, generally this category is rated as Agree. This result

simply says that the market management strongly convinced that it is the sole obligation of every market vendor to secure business permit and have it renewed upon expiration in which the same must be conspicuously displayed at his/her stall for ready inspection; to keep his /her stall in good sanitary condition at all times, and by having a garbage can or receptacle of his/her own.

Table 2.1.5 Extent of Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors as perceived by management

No	Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors	Mean	SD	Description
1	To have his/her picture and that of his/her helpers conveniently framed and hung up conspicuously in the stall.	3.1500	.93330	Agree
2	To secure business permit and have it renewed upon expiration. The same must be conspicuously displayed at his/her stall for ready inspection.	4.5500	.68633	Strongly Agree
3	To keep his/her stall in good sanitary condition at all times, by having a garbage can or receptacle of his/her own.	4.6000	.50262	Strongly Agree
4	To pay promptly without demand his/her market dues and other fees at the Municipal office. In case his/her failure to do, pay all fines and penalties accruing thereto.	4.2500	.63867	Agree
5	To present and have their weighing scales calibrated and sealed at the Municipal office.	4.5000	.51299	Strongly Agree
Average Mean		4.2100	.38648	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50- 5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49=Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49-Uncecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49-Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.2 By Market Vendors

2.2.1 On administration and supervision

Table 2.2.1 shows the extent of market administration and supervision as perceived by vendors. The mean score of 4.1350 with standard deviation of .36108 is generally rated as Agree under this category. This means that the market vendors in Jolo, Sulu are amenable to market policies that the Mayor shall exercise powers of administration and supervision and control overall markets in the municipality. Also, they believe that the market administrator shall coordinate with other offices in maintaining proper hygiene and sanitation and enforces strictly all provisions of municipal ordinances related to market administration.

Table 2.2. 1 Extent of market administration and supervision as perceived by vendors

No	Administration and Supervision	Mean	SD	Description
1	The Mayor shall exercise powers of administration and supervision and control overall markets in the municipality.	4.3500	.62563	Agree
2	The treasurer accepts and records all application for markets stall.	3.9500	.70173	Agree
3	The treasurer shall be responsible for awards of stall, collect and receive all kinds of rentals, including license and taxes.	3.8900	.69479	Agree
4	The market administrator shall have the direct and immediate supervision over the market, slaughter	4.0800	.63054	Agree
5	The market administrator shall exercise immediate overall market collectors and other personnel in the market.	4.1100	.63397	Agree
6	The market administrator shall coordinate with other offices in maintaining proper hygiene and sanitation and enforces strictly all provisions of municipal ordinances related to market administration.	4.2200	.59595	Agree
7	The market administrator shall require all market collectors to turn over their respective collection every day, act as property custodian all property of the market.	4.1100	.64971	Agree
8	The market administrator shall prohibit the building and construction in the market or premises hereof any form of extension of stalls, shade or tables beyond the lease area.	4.1600	.70668	Agree
9	The market administrator shall inspect and supervises market and slaughter house to ensure that all livestock are properly cared for, butchered and sold in conformity with regulation of the National Meat Inspection Commission.	4.2000	.58603	Agree
10	The market administrator shall inspect dressed meat (chicken) and determine its fitness for human consumption.	4.2800	.66788	Agree
Average Mean		4.1350	.36108	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50- 5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49= Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49= Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.2.2 On safety and security

Table 2.2.2 reveals the extent of safety and security as perceived by vendors. With overall mean score of 4.5860 and standard deviation of .35986, this component is generally rated as Strongly Agree. This result shows that the market vendors do agree, in order to maintain peace and order, that there shall be security personnel assigned in the market to ensure safe and secured market environment; the security personnel shall patrol and perform sentinel activity within the market and slaughter house premises; and the security personnel shall report violation of laws, ordinances to proper law enforcing agencies.

Table 2.2.2 Extent of safety and security as perceived by vendors

No	Safety and Security	Mean	SD	Description
1	There shall be security personnel assigned in the market to ensure safe and secured market environment.	4.6800	.46883	Strongly Agree
2	The security personnel shall patrol and perform sentinel activity within the market and slaughter house premises.	4.6300	.48524	Strongly Agree
3	The security personnel shall report violation of laws, ordinances to proper law enforcing agencies.	4.6100	.52982	Strongly Agree
4	The security personnel shall make inventory of losses of property if there is any.	4.4200	.62247	Agree
5	The security personnel shall sound alarms in case of emergencies and operates fire extinguisher or inform the Bureau of Fire Protection.	4.5900	.51434	Strongly Agree
Average Mean		4.5860	.35986	Strongly Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50- 5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49=Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49=Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.2.3 On Hygiene and Sanitation

Table 3.2.3 tackles the on the extent of Hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by vendors. It can be gleaned from this table that a mean score of 4.3428 with standard deviation of .30048 is generally rated as Agree. This simply express that the market vendors are convinced that all merchandise, goods and textiles offered for sale in the market shall be so arranged so that no portion of the alleys shall be obstructed, and the that the floor stands, and all other places of things used for exposing the same can be easily and perfectly clean; market cleaning schedule will be at night time, early dawn or on time to prevent inconvenience to the vendors and the market going public; garbage and waste shall be regularly hauled to the dumpsite; and sufficient potable water shall be provided by the Municipal for use in cleaning fresh

foodstuffs in the market. This result implies that the market vendors are deeply concerned on the cleanliness of the market areas.

Table 2.2.3 Extent of Hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by vendors

No	Hygiene and Sanitation	Mean	SD	Description
1	All merchandise, goods and textiles offered for sale in the market shall be so arranged so that no portion of the alleys shall be obstructed, and the that the floor stands, and all other places of things used for exposing the same can be easily and perfectly clean.	4.4400	.591 52	Agree
2	All merchandise, goods, articles or foodstuffs offered for sale shall be protected from all kinds of insects and vermin and placed in such manner as authorized by the municipal officials.	4.3400	.516 79	Agree
3	The market cleaners will be closely supervised by the Municipal Health Officer or his representative.	4.2100	.498 38	Agree
4	Market cleaning schedule will be at night time, early dawn or noon time to prevent inconvenience to the vendors and the market going public.	4.5000	.541 23	Strongly Agree
5	All fixed stall vendors shall install garbage receptacles in their respective stalls.	4.3500	.538 89	Agree
6	Garbage and waste shall be regularly hauled to the dumpsite.	4.5657	.518 27	Strongly Agree
7	Sufficient potable water shall be provided by the Municipal for use in cleaning fresh foodstuffs in the market.	4.5600	.556 32	Strongly Agree
8	Livestock ante-mortem and post-mortem inspections of dressed meat shall be conducted before the animals are butchered and before the dressed meat are taken out of the abattoir.	4.0000	.619 55	Agree
9	The meat inspector shall submit regularly reports to the local authorities on the conditions in the slaughter house.	4.0300	.576 56	Agree
10	The Municipal Health Officer is tasked with the keeping the market in a clean, healthful and sanitary condition.	4.4400	.556 32	Agree
Average Mean		4.3428	.300 48	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50 - 5.00 Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49=Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49= Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.2.4 On Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors

Table 2.2.4 deals with the extent of prohibit acts by the market vendors as perceived by vendors. The overall mean score of 4.0190 with standard deviation of 38210 is generally rated as Agree. This means

that the market vendors do adhere to the provisions, among other things, that no unauthorized making of extensions of stalls beyond leased areas and/or utilizing pathways for displays of goods; no short weighing and false measuring including tampering of standard weights and measures; and no displaying and selling of illegal products/items.

Table 2.2.4 Extent of prohibit acts by the market vendors as perceived by vendors.

No	Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors	Mean	SD	Description
1	Selling of goods not designated in assigned areas.	4.2300	.633 33	Agree
2	Unauthorized making of extensions of stalls beyond leased areas and/or utilizing pathways for displays of goods.	4.3000	.594 59	Agree
3	Short weighing and false measuring including tampering of standard weights and measures.	4.6600	.713 79	Strongly Agree
4	Bringing in motorcycles, bicycles, push charts and the like inside the market compound.	3.5700	.977 06	Agree
5	Utilizing any of the stalls or market spaces as residence or living quarters.	3.9400	.749 68	Agree
6	Littering, vandalizing and improper use of comfort rooms (if there is any) and non-observance and cooperation on cleanliness and orderliness.	4.2000	.724 74	Agree
7	Selling or transferring the privilege to lease the stalls or spaces or permitting another person to conduct business therein.	3.4100	.922 17	Agree
8	Bringing in of children below 10 years old by market vendors inside the market premises.	3.3500	.783 35	Agree
9	Operation of any forms of gambling or betting and videoke machine and the like.	3.9500	.657 13	Agree
10	Display and selling of illegal products/items.	4.5800	.638 50	Strongly Agree
Average Mean		4.0190	.382 10	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50- 5.00-Strongly Agree;
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49- Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49-Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49- Disagree,
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

2.2.5 On Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors

Table 3.2.5 illustrates the extent of hygiene and sanitation program as perceived by vendors. With an overall mean score of 4.1380 and standard deviation of 39049, this category is rated as Agree. This result simply tells that the market vendors at Jolo, Sulu, knowing their personal obligations, are much willing to present and have their weighing scales calibrated and sealed at the Municipal office; to keep their stalls in good sanitary condition at all times, by having a garbage can or receptacle of their own; and to secure

business permit and have it renewed upon expiration in which the same must be conspicuously displayed at his/her stall for ready inspection.

Table 2.2.5 Extent of Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors as perceived by vendors

No	Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors	Mean	SD	Description
1	To have his/her picture and that of his/her helpers conveniently framed and hung up conspicuously in the stall.	3.6900	.734 37	Agree
2	To secure business permit and have it renewed upon conspicuously expiration. The same must be conspicuously displayed at his/her stall for ready inspection.	4.1300	.485 24	Agree
3	To keep his/her stall in good sanitary condition at all times, by having a garbage can or receptacle of his/her own.	4.3300	.513 55	Agree
4	To pay promptly without demand his/her market dues and other fees at the Municipal office. In case his/her failure to do, pay all fines and penalties accruing thereto.	3.9400	.678 98	Agree
5	To present and have their weighing scales calibrated and sealed at the Municipal office.	4.6000	.765 41	Agree Strongly Agree
Average Mean		4.1380	.390 49	Agree

Rating Scales:

- 5) 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree,
- 4) 3.50 - 4.49= Agree;
- 3) 2.50 - 3.49=Undecided;
- 2) 1.50 - 2.49-Disagree;
- 1) 1.00 - 1.49-Strongly Disagree

3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to gender, age and monthly income?

3.1 By Gender

Table 3.1 emphasizes the difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors when data are categorized according to gender. Under the different programs of the market management, it can be seen on this table that none among the means difference scores with corresponding t-

Values are significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. This means that regardless of male or female, the market vendors do not differ in their perceptions toward the obeying to market rules and regulations, proper observance of cleanliness and peace and order in the market place. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management and vendors when data are categorized according to gender" is hereby accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors when data are categorized according to gender.

Variables		Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Gender							
Administration and Supervision	Male	4.1065	.35291	.07776	-1.045	.299	Not Significant
	Female	4.1842	.37455				
Safety and Security	Male	4.5645	.36309	.05654	-.761	.449	Not Significant
	Female	4.6211	.35653				
Hygiene and Sanitation	Male	4.3371	.29876	.01290	-.208	.836	Not Significant
	Female	4.3500	.30646				
Prohibit Acts by the Market Vendors	Male	4.0656	.36915	.09856	1.256	.212	Not Significant
	Female	3.0579	.39975				
Obligatory Duties and Responsibilities of the Market Vendors	Male	4.1323	.34536	.01511	-.187	.852	Not Significant
	Female	4.1474	.45957				
	Female						

3.2 By Age

Table 3.2.1 shows the difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management in terms of age. Within this component, it is noticeable that none among the mean squares score with the corresponding F-values is significant at Alpha-0.05. This means that the market management staffs, despite of their age differences, do not differ in their judgments toward their expectations on the proper implementation of the market policies and programs. This implies that gender does not influence the perceptions of the market management. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management when data are categorized according to age" is accepted.

Table 3.2.1 Difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market management in terms of age.

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	Si.	Description
Administrative & Supervision Between Groups	.228	2	.144	.841	.449	Not Significant
Within Groups	2.302	17	.135			
Total	2.530	19				
Safety & Security Between Groups	.258	2	.129	.618	.550	Not Significant
Within Groups	3.550	17	.209			

Total	3. 808	19				
Hygiene & Sanitation Between Groups	.021	2	.010	.138	.872	Not Significant
Within Groups	1.291	17	.076			
Total	1.312	19				
Prohibited Acts by the Vendors Between Groups	.031	2	.015	.476	.634	Not Significant
Within Groups	.322	17	.032			
Total	.352	19				
Obligatory Duties and responsibilities of the Vendors Between Groups	.245	2	.123	.569	.577	Not Significant
Within Group	3.667	17	.216			
Total	3.912	19				

Table 3.2.2 shows the difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that non among the mean squares scores is significant t at Alpha-0.05. This means that, like those people in the market management, these market vendors do not differ in their perceptions toward the proper implementation of the market policies and programs. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors when data are categorized according to age" is accepted.

Table 3.2.2 Difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors in terms of age.

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	Si.	Description
Administrative & Supervision Between Groups	.488.	2	.244	1.800	.171	Not Significant
Within Groups	13.140	97				
Total	13.628	99	.135			
Safety & Security Between Groups	.045	2	.022	.177	.838	Not Significant
Within Groups	12.315	17	.127			

Total	12.360	19				
Hygiene & Sanitation Between Groups	.095	2	.143	.918	.403	Not Significant
Within Groups	9.235	17	.156			
Total	9.330	19				
Prohibited Acts by the Vendors Between Groups	.286	2	.015	.476	.634	Not Significant
Within Groups	15.115	17	.032			
Total	15.402	19				
Obligatory Duties and responsibilities of the Vendors Between Groups	.145	2	.073	.450	.639	Not Significant
Within Group	15.621	17	.161			
Total	15.766	19				

3.3 By Income

Table 3.3 illustrates the difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors in terms of income. It is noticeable on this that in categories Safety & Security and Hygiene & Sanitation, the result revealed that these variables obtained the mean square of 502, $F=4.021$, with $p=.021$ and mean square of .636, $F=8.095$, with $p=.001$ which are both significant at alpha .05. This means that market vendors do differ in their perceptions toward safety and cleanliness in the market areas. In other words, those vendors who earn 1,000-3,000 differ in beliefs toward safety and security in the market areas as against those whose earnings are peg at 3,000-6,000 and 6,000-9,000. This result implies that monthly income influences market vendors' beliefs and judgments toward the programs of the market management. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors when data are categorized according to income" is rejected.

Table 3.3 Difference on the extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors in terms of income.

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	Si.	Description
Administrative & Supervision Between Groups	.229	2	.115	.844	.433	Not Significant

Within Groups	13.172	97	.136			
Total	13.402	99				
Safety & Security Between Groups	1.004	2	.502	4.021	.021	Significant
Within Groups	12.108	17	.125			
Total	13.112	19				
Hygiene & Sanitation Between Groups	1.272	2	.636	8.095	.001	Significant
Within Groups	7.622	17	.079			
Total	8.894	19				
Prohibited Acts by the Vendors Between Groups	.060	2	.030	.202	.817	Not Significant
Within Groups	14.347	17	.148			
Total	14.407	19				
Obligatory Duties and responsibilities of the Vendors Between Groups	.390	2	.195	1.285	.281	Not Significant
Within Group	14.706	17	.152			
Total	15.096	19				

*Significant at Alpha 0.05

Post Hoc Analysis using Scheff's Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to monthly income to have different levels of mean in areas of market management programs. The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 3.3.1 indicates that only in Safety & Security and Hygiene & Sanitation to have significant difference.

It can be noted that the difference in the means of Safety & Security and Hygiene & Sanitation by components of the groups compared by way of lower group mean minus higher group mean shows that 6,000-9,000 obtained the mean difference of - 34667 with Standard Error of 12352 and p-.023 over 1,000-3,000 in safety & security.

Table 3.3.1. Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in extent of the programs of Jolo Municipal Government as perceived by market vendors in terms of income

Safety & Security	1-3T minus 6-9T	3-6T minus 6-9T	6-9T minus 3-6T
Mean Difference	-.34667*	-.18806	-.15861
Standard Error	.12352	.09380	.10092
Sig	.023	.140	.295
Hygiene & Sanitation	1-3T minus 3-6T	1-3T minus 6-9T	3-6T minus 6-9T
Mean Difference	-.28284*	-.32667*	-.04383
Standard Error	.07442	.09800	.08007
Sig	.001	.005	.861

*Significant at Alpha-0.05

Likewise, in Hygiene & Sanitation category, 3,000-6,000 obtained a mean difference of 34667, with standard error of 12352 and $p=.023$ over 1,000-3,000. So no other group of market vendors are supposed to have better level of perceptions than the 6,000-9,000 with regards to judging the proper implementation of safety and security as well as the hygiene and sanitation at the market areas of the Municipality of Jolo.

4. What are the perceptions of the management and market and sidewalk vendors on prospects on how to improve the Jolo Public Market?

4. Prospects on the Improvement of the Jolo Public Market.

Shown in Table 4, are the recommendations of the Management and Market and Sidewalk Vendors on how to improve the Jolo Public Market. The data are arranged and ranked according to what are frequently recommended by the respondents. However, only few among the respondents have able to recommend.

Table 4. The recommendations of the Management and Market and Sidewalk Vendors on the Improvement of the Jolo Public Market.

No	Management	Rank
1.	Presence of policemen and security personnel in the market place.	1 st
2.	Proper implementation of laws and ordinances of Market place.	2 nd
3.	Prompt payments of dues and licenses to the proper collecting authority.	3 rd
4.	Market vendors shall at all times stay in their proper places, and avoid selling their product in the pedestrian lanes.	4 th

5.	Sanguniang or Municipal council should craft ordinances significant to proper administration of the market.	5 th
6.	Market management should do their tasks to improve our market.	6 th
7.	Market vendors shall be responsible and participative in maintaining cleanliness and safety in the Jolo Public Market.	7 th
8.	Build more buildings for market vendors.	8 th
Market and Sidewalk Vendors		
1.	Daily collection of garbage and watering of the place where the fish is usually sold.	1 st
2.	Improve the drainage system.	2 nd
3.	Provide more lights and comfort rooms for public and market vendors' use.	3 rd
4.	Proper arrangement and placing of the ice boxes.	4 th
5.	Improve or renovate the market buildings.	5 th
6.	Regular sanitary inspections.	6 th
7.	Segregation of wastes from bio degradable to non-bio-degradable.	7 th
8.	Place a signage to warn and inform the public in keeping the Jolo Public Market clean.	8 th
9.	Provision of ice storage.	9 th
10.	Market vendors should not sell their products along the pathways, pavements and sidewalks.	10 th
11.	Parking area for vehicles.	11 th

Reflected in the Table on the recommendations of the Management, the issue on security and safety of the market ranked first, followed by the issues on proper implementation of market laws or ordinances and prompt payment of the market fees and renewal of the licenses, ranked second and third, respectively. These data, imply that security and safety, observance and proper implementation of the laws, and proper collection of the market fees and renewal of the licenses are the utmost concerns of the management. Hence, being in the government, which has inherent task to provide basic services and assurance of peace and order among the Jolo constituents.

While on the side of the Market and Sidewalk vendors, the issue on collection of garbage and watering of the place where the fish is usually sold, ranked first. This is followed by the issues on improvement of the drainage system and provision of more lights and comfort rooms for public and market vendors, which ranked second and third, respectively. These data suggest that the most pressing concerns of the market and sidewalk vendors are the cleanliness and sanitation aspects of the market. It is therefore

true, as observed by anyone who frequent the Jolo Public Market, the place is not clean, the garbage is not properly collected and the obvious absence of water and light facilities and comfort rooms.

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